

FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES.

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ANNOTATION.

The article provides a brief historical overview of the development of fractional computing, and considers special functions of mathematical analysis for working with non-integer derivatives. Caputo and Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives are considered.

Key words: Caputo fractional derivative , fractional integrals, mathematical analysis, Riemann integral, graphs, fractional integro-differential calculus, fibrous polymers, deformation.

ANNOTATION.

The paper provides a brief historical overview of the development of fractional arithmetic, considering the special functions of mathematical analysis for working with non-integer products. Fractional-order derivatives of Caputo and Riemann-Liouville are considered.

Key words: Caputo fractional product, fractional integrals, mathematical analysis, Riemann integral, graphs, fractional integro - differential calculus, fibrous polymers, deformation.

Fractional derivatives and their calculation methods.

Many problems of mathematical physics can be described in the form of partial differential equations. In such a description, it is possible to naturally determine the solution of boundary problems corresponding to it, and at the same time, certain methods can be applied to their solution. Processes occurring in nature are more accurately represented by fractional equations. By now, due to the increased demand for their application to practical problems, research has intensified, and the formulation of problems has been clarified, and completely new types of problems have been put before experts.

Suppose that $[a, b]$ a bounded interval in $\alpha \in C(\Re(\alpha) \geq 0)$ the segment and R is

$D_{a+}^{\alpha} [y(t)](x) \equiv (D_{a+}^{\alpha} y)(x)$ and $D_{b-}^{\alpha} [y(t)](x) \equiv (D_{b-}^{\alpha} y)(x)$ let be fractional derivatives in the Riemann-Louisville sense α

$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$ in Caputo's sense $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ ($\Re(\alpha) \geq 0$) Fractional derivatives in the Riemann-Louisville sense α are defined using fractional derivatives as follows:

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) := \left(D_{a+}^\alpha \left[y(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(a)}{k!} (t-a)^k \right] \right)(x), \quad (1.1)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) := \left(D_{b-}^\alpha \left[y(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(b)}{k!} (b-t)^k \right] \right)(x), \quad (1.2)$$

here, if $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$, $n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$, if α is a natural number, $n = \alpha$ then

These (1.1) and (1.2) are called left and right derivatives in the Caputo sense, respectively.

If $0 < \Re(\alpha) < 1$ so, the left and right derivatives in the Caputo sense, corresponding to (1.1) and (1.2), are defined as follows:

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{a+}^\alpha [y(t) - y(a)])(x), \quad (1.3)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{b-}^\alpha [y(t) - y(b)])(x). \quad (1.4)$$

If $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$ and are $y(x)$ the fractional derivatives $(D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ of the function $({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and in the Caputo sense, and $({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $(D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$ If there are derivatives in the Riemann-Louisville sense, then the following equalities hold:

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(a)}{\Gamma(k - \alpha + 1)} (x-a)^{k-\alpha}, \quad (1.5)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(b)}{\Gamma(k - \alpha + 1)} (b-x)^{k-\alpha}, \quad (1.6)$$

here ($n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$).

If $0 < \Re(\alpha) < 1$ so, then it is as follows $({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) - \frac{y(a)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} (x-a)^{-\alpha}$,

$$(1.7) \quad ({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) - \frac{y(b)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} (b-x)^{-\alpha}. \quad (1.8)$$

If $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$, $y(a) = y'(a) = \dots = y^{(n-1)}(a) = 0$, then ($n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$) Caputo and Riemann - Louisville, i.e

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) \quad (1.9)$$

will be

If it's like that $y(b) = y'(b) = \dots = y^{(n-1)}(b) = 0$, then

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) \quad (1.10)$$

will be In particular $0 < \Re(\alpha) < 1$, $y(a) = 0$ if

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) \quad (1.11)$$

will be If it's like that $y(b) = 0$, then

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = (D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) \quad (1.12)$$

will be

If $\alpha \in N$ so, then derivatives in the Caputo sense overlap with ordinary derivatives, i.e.:

$$({}^C D_{a+}^n y)(x) = y^{(n)}(x) \quad (1.13)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^n y)(x) = (-1)^n y^{(n)}(x) \quad (1.14)$$

will be In order for a function to have derivatives in the Caputo sense, it must have fractional derivatives in the Riemann-Louisville sense of this function. For this $y(x) \in AC^n[a, b]$ to be, $y(x)$ the function must be an absolute function.

Theorem 1.1. $\Re(\alpha) \geq 0$ and $n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$ let it be. If $y(x) \in AC^n[a, b]$, then $[a, b]$ there are fractional derivatives in the Caputo sense at $({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$

a) if $\alpha \notin N$, $({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$ are of the form:

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y^{(n)}(t) dt}{(x-t)^{\alpha-n+1}} =: (I_{a+}^{n-\alpha} D^n y)(x) \quad (1.15)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_x^b \frac{y^{(n)}(t) dt}{(t-x)^{\alpha-n+1}} =: (-1)^n (I_{b-}^{n-\alpha} D^n y)(x) \quad (1.16)$$

in this, $D = \frac{d}{dx}$.

In particular, $0 < \Re(\alpha) < 1$ if and $y(x) \in AC[a, b]$

$$({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y'(t) dt}{(x-t)^\alpha} = (I_{a+}^{1-\alpha} Dy)(x), \quad (1.17)$$

$$({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x) = -\frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_x^b \frac{y'(t) dt}{(t-x)^\alpha} =: -(I_{b-}^{1-\alpha} Dy)(x) \quad (1.18)$$

will be

a) if $\alpha \in N$ so, $({}^C D_{a+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b-}^\alpha y)(x)$ are determined by formulas (1.13) and (1.14), respectively. In particular,

$$({}^C D_{a^+}^0 y)(x) = ({}^C D_{b^-}^0 y)(x) = y(x) \quad (1.19)$$

will be

Similar to the above theorem, if $y(x)$ a function n belongs to the class of continuous functions with ordered derivatives, then the following theorem holds.

Theorem 1.2. $\Re(\alpha) \geq 0$ and $n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$ let it be. If $y(x) \in C^n[a, b]$, then $[a, b]$ there are fractional derivatives in the Caputo sense at $({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(x)$

a) if $\alpha \notin N$ so, $({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(x)$ are determined by formulas (1.15) and (1.16). In addition, the following equations are relevant:

$$({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(a) = ({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(b) = 0. \quad (1.20)$$

In particular, $0 < \Re(\alpha) < 1$ if is determined by formulas (1.17) and (1.18), respectively.

b) if $\alpha \in N$ so, $({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(x)$ are determined by formulas (1.13) and (1.14), respectively. In particular,

$$({}^C D_{a^+}^0 y)(x) = ({}^C D_{b^-}^0 y)(x) = y(x) \quad (1.21)$$

will be

Result 1.1. $\Re(\alpha) \geq 0$ and $n = [\Re(\alpha)] + 1$ let it be.

a) if $y(x) \in C^n[a, b]$, then $({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(x)$ in the sense of Caputo, fractional derivatives $C[a, b]$ belong to the class. In addition, the following assessments are relevant:

$$\|{}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y\|_{C_a} \leq k_\alpha \|y\|_{C^n} \text{ and } \|{}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y\|_{C_b} \leq k_\alpha \|y\|_{C^n}, \quad (1.22)$$

here

$$k_\alpha = \frac{(b-a)^{n-\Re(\alpha)}}{|\Gamma(n-\alpha)|[n-\Re(\alpha)+1]}. \quad (1.23)$$

b) if $\alpha \in N$, $({}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y)(x)$ and $({}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y)(x)$ s $C[a, b]$ belong to the class. In addition, the following equations are relevant:

$$\|{}^C D_{a^+}^\alpha y\|_{C_a} \leq k_\alpha \|y\|_{C^n} \text{ and } \|{}^C D_{b^-}^\alpha y\|_{C_b} \leq k_\alpha \|y\|_{C^n} \quad (1.24)$$

1) $f(t) = 1$ $0 < \alpha < 1$ Compute the fractional derivative in the Caputo sense.

$${}^C D^\alpha [1] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\xi)^{1-\alpha-1} (1)' d\xi = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t 0 d\xi = \quad (1.25)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} C|_0^t = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} (C - C) = 0$$

(1.25) it follows that the constant number $0 < \alpha < 1$ the Caputo derivative in the interval is zero.

1) $f(t) = t^\mu \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$ Compute the fractional derivative in the Caputo sense.

$$\begin{aligned} {}^c D^\alpha f(t) &= I^{1-\alpha} \frac{d}{dt} (t^\mu) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\xi)^{1-\alpha-1} (\xi^\mu)' d\xi = \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t \mu (t-\xi)^{-\alpha} \xi^{\mu-1} d\xi \left[\begin{array}{l} \xi = ty \\ d\xi = tdy \end{array} \right] = \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^1 \mu t^{\mu-\alpha} (1-y)^{-\alpha} y^{\mu-1} dy = \frac{\mu t^{\mu-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} B(\mu, 1-\alpha) = \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\mu+1)}{\Gamma(\mu+1-\alpha)} t^{\mu-\alpha} \quad (1.26) \end{aligned}$$

1) $f(t) = e^t \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$ Compute the fractional derivative in the Caputo sense.

Calculating similarly to Caputo's derivation above, we get the formula below.

$${}^c D^\alpha (e^t) = t^{1-\alpha} E_{1,2-\alpha}(t) \quad (1.27)$$

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